

Gel water adsorbs non-H⁺ monovalent cations

Johan Nygren

johanngrn@gmail.com

Adsorption of monovalent cations solidifies gel

Water can be ordered into an ice-like phase of water when it contacts surfaces that favour that structure (Pollack, 2013). This phase does not form vertical hydrogen bonds between the ice lattice sheets, because the high thermal energy on top of the repelling force between the sheets breaks the bonds.

Figure 1 Water ordered by scaffolds forms a gel form of ice that lacks the vertical hydrogen bonds. Image reworked from Pollack, 2013.

The repelling force between the lattice sheets can be overcome by a stronger attractive force, from an atom with a higher number of protons in the nucleus. Normally, the attractive force falls off rapidly down the rows of the periodic table because of increased distance to the nucleus. But in the ice crystal, the distance of attraction is not limited by the atomic radius, it is limited by the repelling force between the sheets.

Figure 2 The stronger attractive force of potassium, owing to the higher number of protons, lets it substitute H⁺ in the ice crystal. Image reworked from Pollack, 2013.

Salt solutions have higher surface tension

It is known since the early 20th century that solutions of inorganic salts in water have greater surface tensions than that of the pure solvent (Heydweiller, 1910; Onsager, 1934; Dole, 1937; Belton, 1937;

Ariyama, 1937). This fits with the theory that the gel phase can substitute the excluded hydrogen ions with other monovalent cations like sodium and potassium.

Cells selectively adsorb potassium

Cells are known to selectively accumulate potassium ions over sodium ions, and the bulk-phase theory suggests that this is because of selective adsorption of potassium (Ling, 1962). Sidney Fox has demonstrated that “proto cells” formed by boiling protein in water, will accumulate potassium up to 1600x that in the external medium (Ishima, 1981). The explanation for the selective adsorption could be that potassium (and sodium to a lesser extent) is able to replace the excluded proton.

Do monovalent cations invade gel phase water? Implications for osmosis

Osmosis has been shown to also alter the pH of the compartments, forming an alkaline water compartment and an acidic salt compartment (Zhao and Pollack, 2009). This fits with the theory that the gel phase is a “magnet” for monovalent cations like sodium (and even more potassium, why cells favour it.) The monovalent cation in the salt compartment could invade the gel in the water compartment, adsorbed into it by electrostatic attraction. This change in electrostatic charge in the two compartments would force the movement of hydrogen ions from the water compartment to the salt compartment. The hydrogen ions pair with the salt anion, forming an acid, and the surplus hydroxide ions in the alkaline compartment pair with the cation that was adsorbed into the gel water.

Once an alkaline water compartment and acidic salt compartment has formed, they are equivalent to compartments in an acid-base electrochemical cell (Weng, 2019). There will be oxygen evolution reactions in the alkaline compartment, and electrons moving to the salt compartment cause oxygen reduction reactions.

In case osmosis experiments are not usually done in vacuum, there is externally supplied oxygen gas from the air. Gerald Pollack has documented in his *The Fourth Phase of Water* that the gel membrane becomes impenetrable, it could hold out water against gravity.

Since oxygen is fed into the system from the outside, as long as the hydrogen ions have moved initially, water can be produced in the salt compartment and split in the water compartment. The impenetrable membrane prevents the newly formed water in the salt compartment from flowing back into the water compartment.

Figure 3 The osmotic membrane becomes impermeable to water once the electrostatic movement of hydrogen ions has stabilized. Image from Pollack, 2013.

The redox balance between water and oxygen causes phenomena of osmosis

The electrical potential that forms between the water (alkaline) and salt (acidic) compartments during osmosis (Loeb, 1921; Pollack, 2009; 2013) is a result of a shift in the redox balance between the dioxide and dihydro state of oxygen, from the loss of hydrogen ions from the alkaline compartment. The balance is restored by the transfer of electrons from the water to the salt compartment.

Figure 4 The redox pair water and oxygen seen as an equilibrium. The exclusion of protons shifts the redox balance between the dihydro and dioxide state of oxygen, creating a potential for electric current.

The role of sodium in the cell, depolarization

The role of sodium in the cell is as an antagonist to potassium. The protoplasm selectively adsorbs potassium because its positive charge is higher when atomic radius is not the limiting factor. The relationship is the reverse in the liquid phase of water. In the liquid phase, the water instead prefers to bond with sodium ions, because their positive charge to atom radius is higher, and distance was only a limiting factor in the gel phase. The exchange of univalent cation to sodium favours the depolarization of protoplasm, and this is why multicellular organisms have maintained the sodium rich extra-cellular space of salt water even as they left the oceans.

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